

ELECTORAL BEHAVIOUR OF BIHAR: NARRATIVES FROM SHERGHATI ASSEMBLY CONSTITUENCY OF GAYA, BIHAR

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Abstract

Bihar has been a successful case in mobilizing Dalits and Other Backward Classes (OBCs) to a political domain with electoral politics from different castes. It emphasized on unreserved constituency to gain further vision into social life and historical background that helps to shape of the contemporary political engagement. Here, some efforts has been raised to present a detailed analysis of a selected district of Bihar- Gaya. Within this, from the Gaya district Sherghati (unreserved) panchayat which is total 40,666 (As of 2011 census date) (4 lakhs + approximately as of 2024 out of which 30% are muslim. It has a strong historical background including monuments and forts and also in political matters including parties like JD. It carries legacy in itself which carries stories courageously. Sherghati is a town of Gaya district with unreserved constituency which is working to provide reservations for their people.

Keywords: *Buddhism, ancient, resources, monuments, tourism, unreserved, town, village*

Introduction

Sherghati (formerly Shergotty) is a town of the Gaya district in Bihar, India. It is surrounded by the Morhar River. The name Shergati means Tigar Valley. It says that emperor of Delhi Sultanate named Farid Khan famous as Sher Shah Suri who defeated Humayun was fond of hunting Sher(tigers) which gave priceless and courageous history to this town. This place was under Chero rule but during 1700 it came under rule of Rohilla chief Azam Khan. In 1857 Raja Jehangir Bux Khan revolted against the British. A meteorite that came from Mars fell here in 1865; it is now kept in London museum and is known as the Shergotty meteorite.

Electoral Profile of Sherghati

The Sherghati assembly segment has a total of 2,32,999 registered voters, including 1,21,853 men and 1,11,133 women. According to the 2008 Delimitation Commission recommendations, the constituency includes Dobhi, Sherghati, and Amas community development blocks.

Looking back at Sherghati's electoral history, in 1957, Shahjehan Mohammad of the Indian National Congress (INC) won against independent candidate Upendra Nath Verma,

List of selected villages in the unreserved constituency Sherghati (226), Gaya district for the field visit.

1. Village Panchayat Prakhand	Majhanpur Chitab Kalan Sherghati	05-06 September, 2016
2. Village Panchayat Prakhand	Kalyanpur Patti Komi	7 th September, 2016
3. Village Panchayat Prakhand	Kusumdihi Nabadihi Komi	8 th September, 2016
4. Village Panchayat Prakhand	Pinsara Saawnkalan Aamas	9 th September, 2016

Field Study of Sherghati

On September 5th, as part of the first phase of our research, we arrived at Gaya railway station. The Mahabodhi Express, which had departed from New Delhi, reached Gaya on time. It is fitting that the train is named after Buddha, as this is the place where he attained enlightenment. After freshening up, we set off for Sherghati, our first research site. As we traveled, my mind was flooded with thoughts, particularly about Gaya's history and its status as a Naxalite-affected region. I recalled the words of William Taylor, the district collector in the mid-19th century, who once described Gaya as:

*"A river without water,
A mountain without trees,
And a man without a mind."*

Amid these reflections, we reached Sherghati police station. It was an entirely unfamiliar place for me, and I took a moment to gather my thoughts on the next steps. I had a structured plan for the day, but the curious stares of the locals made me even more aware of my surroundings. I tried to absorb the atmosphere, observing and understanding the people and the place before proceeding further.

As the first step in our research, I met Amit Kumar, the Block Development Officer, at the Block office. He provided me with a general overview of the area and assured me of his

support throughout the research process. Coincidentally, on September 5, 2016, a meeting of all Panchayat representatives was taking place at the office. We had the opportunity to interact with some of them and discuss various local issues.

After the meeting, we took a shared auto to Majhanpur, a nearby village. My first priority was to meet the village Mukhiya (head). A local villager offered to guide me to the Mukhiya's house but stopped short of accompanying me inside. With a respectful tone, he said, "This is village politics, Saab. I'm sure you understand." I simply nodded and proceeded towards the residence of Poonam Devi, the Mukhiya of Chitab Kalan, a seat reserved for women.

Upon arrival, I found that Poonam Devi was not at home, but her husband, Shree Dharmendra Singh, was present. This moment highlighted a well-known reality in Bihar's local governance—while 50% of Mukhiya seats are reserved for women, in many cases, it is their husbands who hold the real power. Voters often focus not on the woman's name but on her husband's, effectively making him the de facto leader. This phenomenon is so common that it even has a local term—*MP or "Mukhiapati"*—referring to husbands who unofficially take charge of their wife's elected position.

When we inquired about the Mukhiya, we were informed that she had gone to the block office for a meeting. Her husband, Shree Dharmendra Singh, welcomed us and openly admitted, "Since this seat was reserved for women this time, I made my wife contest—and ensured her victory." He spoke with pride, adding that he had personally won the elections multiple times when the seat was unreserved.

Dharmendra Singh expressed frustration with the administration, calling it indifferent and unresponsive, even to elected representatives. He claimed that corruption was rampant in the system. Belonging to the upper-caste Bhumihar community, which is the majority in the village, he credited both his and his wife's electoral success to a combination of his developmental work and caste influence. He also gave us a detailed breakdown of the village layout, explaining how each tola (hamlet) was home to a specific caste group.

Using a sampling method, we decided to interview 22 voters out of the village's total electorate of 552. Our first interview was with Lakhi Devi. The questionnaire had 64 questions, but conducting the interview was not easy. She struggled to understand some of the questions, had no answers for others, and in several instances, seemed hesitant to respond. We had to repeatedly reassure her that her answers would remain confidential and would not be shared.

Another major challenge was the presence of other villagers. As soon as we started the interview, people from her tola gathered around, making comments and trying to influence her

responses. Some even dismissed her, saying, "She knows nothing; if you really want the truth, ask us instead." They would interrupt, attempt to silence her, and even try to answer on her behalf, making it difficult to get her independent perspective.

Lakhia Devi belongs to the Aahir community, a backward caste. Her family consists of six members—she, her husband, and their four children. They live below the poverty line, struggling to make ends meet. When asked about her expectations from the government, she simply said, "What do we need? Just two meals a day, clothes to wear, and work to survive. I don't care about any government because all government schemes only benefit the upper-class people. My husband and I do irregular labor jobs, barely managing to sustain our family." Their home consists of three semi-pucca rooms, and like most of her community, she traditionally votes for the Rashtriya Janata Dal (RJD). However, she has little knowledge of the party's manifesto or policies. What she does know is that Lalu Prasad Yadav has done a lot for her community, helping them earn some dignity.

When asked about the most pressing issues in her village, she listed them in order:

1. Lack of cleanliness and toilets
2. Rampant corruption
3. Unemployment

During our interview at her home, two of her neighbors, Munni Devi and Lakho Devi, joined in. We interviewed them separately, only to find that their struggles mirrored Lakhia Devi's. The specific circumstances of their hardships might vary, but the essence of their problems—poverty, illiteracy, and lack of opportunities—remained the same.

We also spoke with other villagers, including Rekha Devi, Kanti Devi, Barti Devi, Pyaari Devi, and Vinod Yadav. Among them, Vinod Yadav stood out as a well-informed and politically aware individual. Expressing his frustration, he said, "Governments in Delhi and Patna send funds for development, but by the time they reach us, local politicians, officers, and middlemen have already divided them among themselves. Villages are filled with unemployed people. There are no proper houses, no food, no jobs—only hopelessness and fear."

A younger villager, Bittoo, added with disillusionment, "We are trapped in a cursed life of deprivation. We have no skills because we never had the chance to learn. Our daily struggle for survival leaves no time for anything else. I am planning to leave with my friends for the city, where at least we can escape this humiliating life."

Another villager, 42-year-old Badho Yadav, was equally cynical about politics. For him, whether a legislative assembly seat was reserved or unreserved made no difference. "It's

always the same," he said. "Either Saapnath wins or Naagnath (referring to two equally bad choices). Whoever gets elected changes completely. They win with the votes of the poor, but once in power, they forget about us. In fact, they start looking down on us."

His words echoed Karl Marx's famous idea that "religion is the opium of the masses." In reality, society remains divided into two categories:

- The bourgeoisie—those who have wealth and power
- The proletariat—those who don't

Vinod Yadav, the local MLA from Sherghati, has given the Aahir community a sense of pride through his electoral victory. However, as he himself pointed out, "Will caste fill our empty stomachs? No. To eat, we need food, and food comes from employment." He also recalled an anecdote about former Chief Minister Lalu Prasad Yadav, who once remarked, "If everyone gets a job, who will attend our rallies?" This highlights how, beyond political loyalty, many people vote based on emotions rather than real expectations of change.

Interestingly, no one we interviewed had any understanding of the NOTA (None of the Above) option in elections. When we explained it to them, they dismissed it, saying, "If NOTA can't win, what's the point of wasting our vote?" While a Hindu newspaper article had suggested that unreserved category voters in reserved constituencies preferred NOTA, we found no such trend in this village.

Village – Kalyanpur, Panchayat – Patti, Prakhand – Komi

The survey of the Kalyanpur village in Sherghati Vidhan Sabha has been done on 07th September, 2016. In this village total 409 voters are there. Out of 409, 26 voters have been interviewed. Majority of the population belong to scheduled caste which in Bihar known as Dalit and Mahadalit. In Bihar there are total 22 scheduled castes out of which 21 have been identified as Mahadalit which was 18 in initial years. Whereas in the Dalit category, only Dusaadh (Paswaan) community has been recognized. Other than these, Rajput and Extremely Backward Class (EBC) population are also present in the village. Brahmin community is also there in village.

During the field research we met Kali Ravidas, Satan Ram, Annirudh Singh, Sunita Devi, Asha Devi, Tuthiya Devi, Cinta Devi, Raajmati Devi, Shweta Joshi, Nityanand Pandey, Bablal, Bipin Kumar, Arun Kumar Singh, Aman Singh, Manoj Saab and Inder Kumar Saab. This village was comparatively more prosperous than our last studied village. People were more conscious. People have a more prestigious life here. Here, people were more vocal and presenting their views on alcohol ban '*sharaabbandi*'. It is important to mention here that from 1st April, 2016

Bihar government has put a ban on manufacturing and selling of desi sharaab and from 6th April, 2016, government has banned all sorts of alcohol in Bihar.

We started our interview with the 68 years old experienced Nityanand Pandey. Nityanand Pandey ji belongs to the brahmin caste. Have five rooms and in his family 4 adults are there and 3 children. He has retired from the government hospital as Compounder. He said that he will not tell that for which party he has voted in last election. However, he also said that “*hum kisi party kesadsyanahihai*”. (we are not member of any party) When questions were asked about the problem of electricity, education, water, he said that “*sarkaariyojnao ka laabhsirf BPL ketahataane wale parivaaron ko pradankiyajatahai. Jarooratmandissewanchit rah jatehai*”. (only the BPL families get the government benefits. The actual needy doesn't get anything) It seems he has some problem with specific groups and he didn't negate that. He also said he rejected the offer of gifts from political parties during the election time. He said that giving gifts as a bribe to the voters is very common here. But the problem was that none of the respondent said that he/ she took any kind of gifts from any political party.

Pandeyji was very worried about the conditions of the government schools. He said that “*ab vidayalaon ki immaratein to aachihai. domanzila ban gayihailekinpadhai ka str bohokam ho gayahai, girgayahai. Shikshakkebahali me bahut dhandalihai*”. (now the school buildings have become good two stoeryed. But the quality of educations has been drastically deteriorated. Full courruption is there in the recruitment of the teachers) He showed his anger and said that “*bangalmeinpratiyogitapariksha k emadhyam se bahalihotihai. Jabaki Bihar meinbinapadhe hi bantahai*”. (in Bengal, the recruitment happens through competition. Whereas in Bihar, you can become a teacher without studying anything) According to him, education policy of Bihar is in a very deplorable condition and its structure have fully gone vanished.

For the democracy, he feels that one party government is good. For him, Coalition government increases thechances of opportunism. In coalition government, parties, leaders loot the government money. He maintains that people's representative these leaders should be honest. Only the capable, educated and those who are selflessly working for the society should be given more participation. He said that “*today's youth should have a moral, ideal determination. Today, there is no need of worshipping in temple rather the shuddhikaran (purification) of the temple is required*”.

This region is fully affected by both flood and famine. British collector Taylor once said that “*there is no water in the rivers of Gaya*”. However, during the rainy season, Falug river creates

havoc in the region. In this context, environmentalist Anupam Mishr have said that “*flood and famine do not come alone. They are fully planned*”.

When tried to know from Pandeyji that how much the alcohol ban (sharab-bandi) was effective. He angrily said “*ye na band hui hai aur na band hogi. pahle jo 20 me miltatha ab wo 50 meinmiltahai. Police ki kamaibadhihai aur sarkar ka rajswagatahai*”. (This never get stopped and it will never stop in future. Earlier it was available in 20 rs, now it is of 50 rs. Police income has increased and state revenue has decreased)

In village, the difference between the forward and backward class is very visible. Along with the financial difference, the social and cultural difference too is quite evident. One main reason for this is education. The educated man thinks of the society too other than the ‘roti, kapda, makaan’ whereas the hungry man always remains engulfed in the vicious circle of the poverty. How much he tries, he is never able to come out of it. Gradually he becomes a machine who does not have any expectations, emotions or grief. As Marx has said that ‘one time comes when in such a situation, the man gets detached from the society, from the state and from himself too. He feels alienated’.

Dulari Devi who is 45 years old said that “*sarkkarketaraf se shouchalayaunhi logo ko milahai jo rishwatdetehain. Hum itnachhotasagharmeinpaanchbetonkesaathrahtehain. Sadak, galikuchbhinahibanahai. Mukhia bola ki galisadakbnadengejoki ab tak to nahibna. Mukhia ji bole ki abhi card nahibanahai. Hum bhejengeaage to card banega. Chunawkesamay sab aatahai per hum apnamann se vote kartehai. Sarkaari school mein meri potipadhtihai, lekin school meinkuchnahimiltahai. Gaon me pipe line se paaninahiaatahai*”. (only those who gave the bribe they have got the money to make toilet. Mukhia told us that drain, road will be made. But still nothing has been done. Mukhia said that card is not made yet, when I will send then it will be processed. During ekection, everybody usd to come and request but I only listen them and vote as per my wish. My granddaughter studies in government primary school but she does not get any benefit from there. We don’t even get water in the pipe which there in village) She is not very happy with Nitish Lalu government. She said that lots of policies are there in paper but they didn’t get anything. She maintained that alcohol ban is very good. She also said that Modi government is giving gas cylinder at lesser price. They didn’t get any.

The director of GovindBallabh Pant Social Science Institute, Allahabad, Prof. Badri Narayan has rightly said that “*real meaning of democracy is participation*”. In this system, the more you get, the more your expectations increase from the government. Here, every individual wants his

involvement. Otherwise despite problems and grievances, people are satisfied with the Lalu Nitish government. Dulari Devi clearly said that she casts vote so that she will get something. Prabhu Yadav, who is 30 years old and works at the brick factory (etatbhatta), said that “*gaon mein school hai. Mere paas APL (Above Poverty Line) card hai. Jisse riyayatidar per bas telmiltahaiannajnahi. Vote hameshadetehai aur ‘teer’ (party symbol of Janata Dal United JDU)) ko detehai. Kabhi kabhi vote badalbhidetehai. gaon me naalinahihai. Aur colony bhinhaibnahai. Bohot logon ko Indira Aawaskeliye do dobaarrupayamilahai. Hamarejaise logo ko kuchnahimilakabhi*”. (In our village, there is a school. I have APL card. I get oil at the subsidised price from PDS. I always vote for ‘teer’ (JDU symbol) Sometime, I change my voting preference. There is no drainage system and no colonies have been made. Many people have got India Aawas money twice. People like us did not get anything)

Every other respondent have same sets of issues where they complained that they didn’t get what they were entitled for.

Village: Kusumdihi, Panchayat: Nawadihi, Prakhand: Komi

In the fourth day of our study, we reached the Kusumdihi village. This village is situated 3 km away from Gaya-Aurangabad main road. We covered this distance by walking. The problems in this village are rally serious. Indian army have made a camp here which is not a new thing. It is important to know here that land for this camp has been taken by Indian government 50 years ago. But because no construction work for camp has been done yet so people used this land for cattle grazing. In this way, people have a deep connection with the land. Now after the camp has been made finally, Army have closed the road for the local villagers. People protested against it and after that some time limit has been given when the locals can use the road but this facility is for partial time only. Most of the people don’t have their land and the whole village seems to be very deserted. Village seems to be very dirty with no proper cleanliness and sanitation facility; people are forced to live a very inhuman life.

Because of flood, we were not able to visit a part of the village. Road was fully submerged in water and Sukhandi Tola where we have to interview our 6 respondent, we were not able to do that. The rest part we did the interview and the respondents were: Ram Balak Yadav, Pankaj Kumar, Asha Kumari, Dev Charan Yadav, Rupani Devi, Muniya Devi, Kamlesh Mondal, Gauri Devi, Meena Devi, Dilu Yadav, Kesari Devi, Ranju Devi, Sonu Yadav, Phhol Kumari Devi.

After seeing the village of Kusumdihi in Nawadihi panchayat, may be Gandhiji would have considered the parameter of the development with the development of the last man. He took

this concept from Ruskin's 'Unto the last'. Scarcity was rampant in this village and everybody seemed to be very sad, malnourished and directionless. Kesari Devi seemed to be very well informed and she talked about the problems in a very detailed manner. She is also involved with the self help group 'Jeevika'. Despite the sadness, She seemed to very positive that one day their life will change too. They will get rid of their problems one day. In this context, Avtaar Singh Sindhu is getting reminded of when said that "*sabseburahotahai ek sapna ka mar jana*" (the most bad thing is the end of a dream)

When we do course of Research Methodology, again and again we have been taught that while going and reporting from the field, field researcher's own feelings and emotions should not overpower him or the study. But when we see kid eating stale rice then one feels very dejected. There was no point of taking such photos.

When we tried to ask that village conditions are so bad, why don't the leaders, the representatives take any call or notice of such bad conditions then Ramsawroop Yadav, resident of the same village said that "*chunaawke samaya hansaaremuddegaun (gayab) ho jatehai. Hum gaon wale hi ek dusre se pratiespardha, pratidwandita mol letehai. Rupaya, paisa, sharab, jaat, paat aur dharmmukhyamudda ban jatahai*". (During chunaav everything vanishes like anything. We, the village people become competitor of each other. Money, caste, alcohol, etc. become major issues) I got reminded of the base and superstructure where everybody is trying to hold the superstructure here. He further said that "*neta log hum logo ko ek dusrekekilaaf use kartehai. Is prakar is stithikeliye hum bhidoshihaiya un kahein hum hi doshihai. Chunaw me dhanbalka nanganaachchaltahai. NitishLalu kemilne se Lalu ko faydahua. Daru bandh karne se log Nitish se naraajhai. Hazaaron log sharaab pine kewajah se jelmein bandh hai. Jail bhargayahai. Log veranda (corridors) me so raheinhai. Bahar Police paise kamarahihai.*" (Leaders use us against each other. We are also responsible for such situation. In election, money and mafia dominate the whole scene. The alliance between Nitish Lalu had benefitted Lalu. People are angry on Nitish for his move of alcohol ban. Many people are locked up due to drinking the alcohol. Jail is full with such people. People living on the verandas in prison. Police is making the money)

While returning from the village, on the main road, few children started talking to us. One student started crying as if we are some government officials and we can solve all the problems. He said that "*sir, mujherojapnechhote bhai ko teen km paidaljaakar school lekarjanapadtahai*". (Sir, I almost walk three kms to send my younger brother to school. They face many problem and they discussed those problems with us. After meeting them, again we

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continued our journey, many people were returning with their cattles. As it has been mentioned above, now after the camp, only the road has remained the last option for them. The land which they used for grazing and farming has been taken by army and in the lower levels, the land has been fully submerged in the water. I got reminded one poem by Iqbal:

“Khudi ko karbuland etna

Ki khudatujh se puche, bta Teri raza kyahai”

Village: Pindara, Panchayat: Saawnkalan, Prakhand: Aamas

Under Sherghati (226) Vidhan Sabha, Pindara village is situated near old grand truck road at the Delhi-Kolkatta national highway 2. In 2 km north of the village, there is a plateau with no tree. In the rainy season, whole lower area gets submerged under the water. Whereas in no rainy season, the whole area faces terribly crisis of water. The villagers are demanding that parallel to the plateau, a embankment should be made so that within the plateau and the embankment, doab can work as canal and can fulfils the need of the village. At the embankment, slui gate can be made so that for two years the water can be used. 50 years old farmer Parmeshwar Yadav said that *“yah sthiti gaon meinkisisapneke such hone jaisahoga. Gaon kesichainsabandhisamstsamsyoon ka ant ho jayega. Goan ki hariyaliwapaslautaayegi”*. (this will fulfill the biggest dream of the village. The irrigation problem of the village will be solved. The greenery will again come back in the village)

Parmeshwar Yadav is literate. He does farming and taking care of his family. He is politically active too. He is not a affiliated to any political party. But from the conversation, it is evident that he might be favouring RJD. As per him, the village is facing the problems of:

Irrigation and Canal (16)

Lane and Drainage (2)

Road and PulPulia (3)

He doesnot have any knowledge about any kinds of bribe or gifts offered by political party. He had bought a pair of cattle for farming, one cow. He has a kachcha home in which three rooms are there. He maintained that alcohol ban is a good step taken by the government. He said that *“log sab peekarladaikarte the. Ab ye sab bandh hai. Jisse paisa aur pratishthadonobachtahai. Pata nahikabtak tik payegasharabbandilekin etna to tayhai ki sabkofaydahuahaiisse”*. (People drink and fight. Now all these has stopped. This is saving our money and respect both. Do not know how long, the ban will be there but one thing is clear that everyone has got benefit due to the ban) 30 years old village resident Sangeeta Devi said that *“sharabbandiek vardanjaisahaiaasher”*. (alcohol ban is like ablessing for us)

On the electoral behaviour Parmeshwar Yadav said that “*yahan to jaatigataadhar per matdankiyajatahai. Aakhir meinjaat hi kaamaatahai. Sab log apneapnejaatkeliye mar rahein hai. Sarkaar se hamein koi fayadakabhinahimila*”. (Here, people vote on the basis of caste. In the last caste is everything to the people. Every body favours their own caste. We do not get any benefit from the village)

The village has population of almost 800 people which is very mixed. Yadav (aahir), Musahari (Manjhi), Ravidas, Prajapati, Hajaam (nai), Muslims are there. Many youth have already migrated to Delhi Punjab, Mumbai for employment. We saw that one family: Ranjit Vishwkarma with his wife Pooja Devi are ready to leave for Delhi. He is working in a furniture factory in Mayapuri, Delhi. In the village, prosperity is only visible where the money is coming from any migrated job.

In the same village, Mohd. Abdullah Mannan with his four sons have made a pakka house. He maintains that this home is his greatest achievement. He is very sad feeling that due to less money he was not able to provide a good education to his sons. But with lots of hope and happiness he also shared that all his grandchildren are going to school. He has a dream that all these kids should excel in their life and become doctors.

Naagdev Rai who belongs to Kahar caste (EBC) has the objection that “*garibi Rekha keneechekenirdharankeliyeeahertaon se pakkamakan ko hatadenachahiye. Ab yeh atyantaawashyak ho gayahai – beti bahu kesurakshakeliyeyaisebhi ho pakkaghar log ab banawarahein hain. Garibon ko bus isiaadhar per bakisarkaarisuvidhaon se vanchitrakhagayahaikyukiunkepaaspakkagharhai. Aisa nahihonachahiye. Pore zindagikekamai se ek do pakka room jaisetaisesaalonmeinbanatehai aur phirbaki koi bhisuvidhanahimiltihai*”. (From the identification list of the BPL, the condition of cemented house should be removed. Now this is very important. For the security of the ladies, girls of the family, this becomes extremely important to have a cemented house at any cost. The poor people do not get all the government benefits just because they have the cemented house. This should not happen. Whole income of life we spent to make a room somehow in years and they we loose all the benefits) He said that this policy is flawed.

In this village, three girls are doing graduation from the Sherghati situated Zakir Hussain College. Out of three girls, Mamata Kumari, daughter of SardaarRajak, wants to be a teacher. In village everybody respects the educated persons and specifically all have huge regards for the girls those who are studying despite all obstacles. Mahatma Gandhi once said “*if a boy is*

studying then alone he is getting the education. However, if a girl is studying, then whole family gets educated”.

In the community centre of the village, self help group ‘Jeevika’s’ meeting has been organized. Jeevika is a programme through which ladies while working with each other becomes self reliant and developing. All members of jeevika are women. In the contemporary days self help groups have seen a huge expansion and growth. People are getting connecting with it and creating avenues of employment and thus becoming self independent. Kerala’s ‘Kutumbashree’ plan has become worldwide success due to its transparency and responsiveness.

Jay Prakash Manjhi has won for the second time and became the Mukhia/Gram Pradhan. Still people are not happy with his works. His USP is that he is an honest man and illiterate and he is a defactomukhia majorly controlled by powerful groups. Under the mukhia, in the village, ‘jalminar’ (paanitanki) is getting constructed. In Pindara village, under the jalminar, 4-5 taps have been fitted. Out of which 3 taps are working. Under the ministry of Public health, Bihar government, these water tanks are getting constructed.

In this way, it is reminding of the ‘Mountain Man’ Dasrath Manjhi and his determination that “*jab taktodengenahi, tab takchodengenahi*”(till the time we will not break, we will not leave). Today, Pindara village is also waiting for that determination.

In this way, in our first phase of study of four VidhanSabhas – the study of first selected seat Sherghati was completed.

Recently, Sherghati is an urban local body Municipality in Gaya district of Bihar state. There are 20 wards in Sherghati Municipality. It includes

#	Ward Name	Ward No	LGDCCode
1	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.6	6	3629
2	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.7	7	3630
3	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.8	8	3631
4	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.9	9	3632
5	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.10	10	3633
6	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.11	11	3634
7	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.12	12	3635
8	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.13	13	3636
9	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.14	14	3637
10	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.15	15	3638
11	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.16	16	3639
12	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.17	17	3640
13	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.18	18	3641
14	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.19	19	3642

15	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.20	20	3643
16	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.1	1	36841
17	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.2	2	36842
18	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.3	3	36843
19	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.4	4	36844
20	Sherghati (NP) - Ward No.5	5	36845

Conclusion

This study emphasizes a lot about constituencies and political matters of Sherghati. It has a very strong historical and a background full of resources and minerals. Many developments include- girl education, transportation, tourism, growing their cultures, languages from the society. Many political constituencies have started giving reservations to Dalits and Other Backward Classes (OBCs) . Also women are engaged in it. Village development is increasing to value its culture and to grow further in other countries as an ancient place. It highlights the political parties and progress of attitudes in societies for the success in Bihar and its districts. This study focuses on the importance of imposing reservation policies and forming environment which is supportive in political engagements in Bihar, contributing to a more equitable political landscape.(Akhtar,2013).

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